

INTERPRETATION OF ETHNOCULTURAL TABLETS OF THE EPIC "KIRK KIZ"

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Summary

This thesis deals with the ethnocultural aspects of the work of Karakalpak cuisine, they are described primarily described in the epic "Kirk kiz."

Keywords

Epic, dialect, stage, work, creativity, art

Talking about the ethnocultural aspects of the creativity of karakalpak cuisine, we see primarily those described in the epic "Kirk kiz." A number of works have been completed in this direction. Stage works saw the world. They value the ethnocultural features of the local population.

In order to restore and promote the oral creativity of the cuisine of the karakalpak country, a lot of work is also carried out in theatrical art. In particular, the Opera and Ballet Theatre named after Alisher Navoi hosted the musical performance "Kirk kiz" created on the basis of the karakalpak epic directed by Saodat Ismailova. "Kirk kiz" aroused great interest among the audience as one of the works of Shokha, created under the auspices of the international Khan trust for culture and the ministry of culture of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The continuing melodies of the musical program reminded the Japanese of the theatre. Everyone knows that Japanese theatrical art is a huge world of art. There is a famous playwright, Tikamatsu Mondzaemon, who is the Shakespeare of the Japanese. He is a father of Japanese theatre arts, who has summarized the development of drama and historical directions in "kabuki" theatres. The main task of Japanese theatres is to show them solos of national heroes who are considered the history of Japan and the pride of the people.

The director of the work, Saodat Ismailova, musical arranger Dmitry Yanov-Yanovsky, together with the stage designer of light and movement Severin Rem and the author of scenographic texts Camillo Kurmanbekova, made a great contribution to the Uzbek theatre in the direction of a new installation performance.

Currently, theatrical art includes: Documentary theatre based on realism and naturalism, human theatre based on the actions of characters, new drama theatre, performance theatre based on the acts of Chekhov and Ibsen in the 20th century.

According to the legend, the first performance artist was the philosopher Diogenes, who lived in a wooden barrel. The storytelling theatre. "in ancient times, "when influential stories of aspiring hindus governing the world of Isa entered the genre. So, the premiere of the play "Dark Night" was accompanied by the style of Saifiddin. Artists in a symbolic sense unfold the world passing in front of the windows with crowds and trains to the station. The writer's son Daniel dies outside the windows, and his wife leaves the world. Today, the writer will be presented with the biggest awards. And outside the windows, people raised by a kamadan, detained on crutches, rush to leave on trains.

Life will go on again. Mehmonkul may have changed in Islam's translation, but the performance feels dull. Garchand, a writer, that is, the main character, according to all the rules of theatrical art, at the beginning of the dance brought home his clothes and nipples, and then took them out. Opens closed doors.

Despite the fact that the drama was staged according to all the criteria, the stage adventure was distinguished by life outside the window. It may have been influenced by events on stage. The play is a long, hard-fought story. A theatrical performance is not a transfer of nature from this life. Is it interesting that the writer, or maybe someone else, with his head on his feet, has his character? In the age of globalization of the 21st century, people suffered from grief and anger. Theatre is a definite idea, not a demonstration of peace and life around the core.

I write these ideas in the Chimkent City Theatre, bearing in mind that they have many masters - Odiljon Tuganbaev, Dilfuza Ibragimzhonov. Venus, Belymbaev, Zhavlon Sayitov and other actors who can create outstanding works in the future. It follows from the above opinions that "Kashkari Dead Night," staged by the Uzbek Drama Theater of the city of Chimkent, is one of such productions of the National Theater as "Chimildyk." I congratulate Uzbek artists of Kazakhstan on this feat.

After watching "Dark Night," I want to make such an offer. Theatres of Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Turkmenistan, Tatarstan and Turkey should organize their creative trips to Uzbekistan two to three times every year. Art, literature and culture bring people closer together.

Now I return to my basic thoughts and suggestions about 'Kirk kiz. " Instead of general considerations relating to 4 elements. It was necessary to add a chronology of the data of the epic "Kirk kiz." Who are the magpies? Why did he oppose the enemy. In what century did this happen. What people live on the island. In this territory are located: where were the Jayhun and the Aral Sea? Crimeans are the pride of Turkic people.

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